

NOVEL PLANAR EXCITATION METHODS FOR PRINTED ANTENNAS

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INTRODUCTION

A pair of novel methods for exciting planar printed antennas that can be integrated directly into MIC and MMIC applications are described. A new microstrip to slotline transition and a coplanar waveguide (CPW) to slotline transition were used to excite printed dipoles at C band. Both antennas achieved 15 dB return loss and 1 dB of boresight gain at midband.

Although there are currently several techniques for implementing printed baluns both from microstrip to slotline and from CPW to slotline, this paper introduces two new methods for planar, balanced excitation of printed antennas such as a dipole or Vivaldi. Until now, the methods for implementing useful printed baluns have all required fabricating the feed network and the printed antenna on opposite sides of the substrate [2],[3]. The major disadvantages of these techniques is that they are not compatible with MIC and MMIC technology and that they require more complex fabrication procedures. A uniplanar excitation method alleviates both of these problems and allows easy integration of printed antennas into applications such as phased array antennas. The two excitation methods described herein make balanced feeding of printed antennas feasible.

DESIGN DESCRIPTION

Figure 1 shows the topology of the new microstrip to slotline transition which was used to provide a well matched, balanced feed to a $\lambda/4$ dipole antenna. This transition provides power transfer from microstrip to conductor backed slotline by resonating the junction between the two media via a slotline radial stub which is effectively $\lambda/4$ at midband. A slotline taper was then used to transform the impedance between the transition and the dipole antenna which was itself resonated by a slotline shorted stub. Selective insertion of grounding pins in a symmetrical fashion was found to enhance the performance of the transition and these could be implemented using via holes.

The CPW to slotline transition is shown in Figure 2. It provides a well matched, balanced feed to a $\lambda/2$ dipole antenna. The antenna arms were slanted at 30 degrees from the vertical which resulted in a relatively wideband impedance match when compared to the standard dipole used in the previous microstrip to slotline case. The CPW to slotline transition itself provides wideband power transfer by resonating the junction between the two media via a circular hollow patch. Here again, a slotline linear taper

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provides impedance transformation between the CPW and the slotline tuned dipole.

An important consideration is the effect that the dielectric substrate thickness has on the antenna radiation pattern. For instance, the reflection coefficient of an air-dielectric-air interface with a dielectric constant of 10 and thickness of 0.05 inches at 3.9 GHz is .416 which corresponds to a return loss of 7.6 dB. Therefore, choosing a dielectric layer much thicker than 50 mils ($\lambda/60$) or a greater dielectric constant would be expected to impede effective radiation. Caution must be exercised in selecting the appropriate substrate to optimize circuit performance without degrading antenna performance.

RESULTS

For the microstrip fed dipole, the test circuit was constructed on a 50 mil substrate with a relative dielectric constant of 10. The microstrip linewidth was 40 mils. The slotline gap was 2 mils. The radial stub length was 260 mils with a 25 degree angle. The dipole arms were each 400 mils in length and 100 mils in width and the feed gap was 40 mils at the end of the 1/2 inch linear taper. The conductor backing extended to within 100 mils of the antenna. Figure 3 (a) shows the return loss data and Figure 4 (a) the azimuthal radiation pattern for this antenna. It was observed that the test antenna achieved 15 dB return loss over 10 percent bandwidth. The antenna demonstrated a peak gain of approximately 1 dB at 3.9 GHz and a slight preference for radiating in the direction opposite the dielectric layer.

For the CPW fed slanted dipole, the test circuit was fabricated on a 25 mil substrate of relative dielectric constant of 10. The CPW center linewidth was 4 mils. The slotline gap was 2 mils. The circular hollow patch diameter was 120 mils. The dipole arms were 390 mils in length and 100 mils in width. The feed gap was 15 mils at the end of the 1/2 inch linear taper. Figure 3 (b) shows the return loss data and Figure 4 (b) the azimuthal radiation pattern for this antenna. The test antenna achieved over 16 percent bandwidth. The antenna also demonstrated a peak gain of approximately 1dB at 5.3 GHz.

CONCLUSION

Two novel planar fed printed dipoles have been demonstrated. One utilizes a CPW to slotline transition and the other an original microstrip to slotline transition. In both cases, proper selection of dielectric constant and thickness for the substrate relative to the wavelength is required to ensure proper antenna performance. The radiation patterns and return loss measurements for these antennas revealed that excellent performance can be achieved by both feeding methods. These designs are straightforward to implement in MMIC and MIC circuits and allow for easy insertion of printed antennas for a multitude of applications.

REFERENCES

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Figure 1: Topology of the new microstrip to slotline transition and dipole antenna

$\epsilon_r=10$, $h=50$ mils, $M=40$, $R_s=260$, $\theta_s=25$, $Arm=400$.

Figure 2: Topology of the CPW to slotline transition and dipole antenna

$\epsilon_r=10$, $h=25$ mils, $M=4$, $S_s=2$, $D_s=120$, $Arm=390$.

**Figure 3: (a) Return loss of the microstrip to slotline fed dipole antenna
(b) Return loss of the CPW to slotline fed dipole antenna**

Figure 4: Azimuthal radiation patterns for (a) microstrip fed dipole and (b) CPW fed dipole

